

Case study on Semantic Interoperability

Template version 2022-03-12 ☰ F3 Template for recording use cases

Purpose: To expand on and update the EOSC Interoperability framework we have the following four sections related to semantic interoperability to address: “3.2.1 Problems and needs”, “3.2.2 Recommendations”, “5.1.3 Semantic view”, and “5.2.1 Semantic view”

Scope: Gather information from the TF members on existing national and international case studies that illustrate use cases related to how semantic artefacts are used to realise semantic interoperability. Including points on lessons learned, barriers, challenges, and opportunities.

Guidance:

- You do not need to be exhaustive in recording all aspects of the project/organisation that you are looking at and it could be useful to narrow down the case studies to focus on those aspects of semantic interoperability that overlap with your current work
- Feel free to include an introduction/comment that describes how you approached recording a value to an element where the guidance from the template did not provide much help
- Use others’ case studies as examples, see ☰ [PaRI-partners-guide \(draft in progress\)](#) or any of the documents in [Working documents / Case studies and use cases \(TF members only\)](#)

What fields (elements) should the template include?

The following fields are described in the next section and should be used to record information about case studies / use cases in this subgroup:

- SI Case study name
- Case study version
- Current status
- Point of contact
- Reference to “official project title”
- Discipline(s)/domain(s)
- Country(s)/Region(s)
- Time period
- Keywords
- Goals
- Links to TF charter
- Interactions
- Semantic Interoperability layer
- Potential use case(s) or user stories

- Technical Interoperability layer
- Organisational Interoperability layer
- Legal Interoperability layer
- Sustainability considerations
- Key take-home points

Please use the following terms to report unknown/missing values:

Value	Definition
not applicable	The information is inappropriate to report or does not apply to the case study
not collected	The information is not available since it was not collected for the case study
not provided	The information is withheld but may be given at a later stage
restricted access	The information exists but can not be released openly because of privacy concerns

Fields and descriptions

SI Case study name

A title that can be used to reference this case study within the EOSC-A Task Force Semantic Interoperability. Enter value on the next line:

Case study version

The date of the latest change. Enter value on the next line:Current status
Free text description of the status of this case study. Enter value on the next line:

Point of contact

Contact details to the individual or organisation that can answer questions regarding the information recorded in this case study. Responsible for the use case, e-mail address preferred. Enter value on the next line:

Reference to "official project title"

This could be for example the official website and name for the project as funded. Enter value on the next line:

Discipline(s)/domain(s)

The data spaces, research domains or disciplines that this case study represents. Keeping track of this will allow us to assess whether the collection of case studies is disciplinarily representative. Enter values on the next line:

Country(s)/Region(s)

The countries and/or larger/smaller regions that this case study represents. Keeping track of this will allow us to assess whether the collection of case studies is geographically representative. Enter values on the next line:

Time period

The date range for which this case study was recorded. Keeping track of this will support traceability. Enter value on the next line:

Keywords

A short list of terms that can be used to describe / distinguish this case study. Enter value on the next line:

Goals

Brief free text summary of the goals of real-life situations described in this case study (research, societal, technical, etc.), short paragraphs. Keeping track of this will provide context. Enter value on the next line:

Links to TF charter

List of applicable objectives from the TF that are addressed by this case study. See [objectives 1–3 on page 4 and examples on page 7 of the TF](#)

One or more of:

- O1: Explorations into Semantic Interoperability
- O1.1: Select/Recommend common metadata standards for a broad range of ‘data’ (e.g. expanding work of Ojsteršek. 2021)
- O1.2: Suggest next steps in the development of catalogues for metadata standards
- O1.3: Evolve syntactic interoperability for data formats, metadata schemas and services
- O1.4: Support the alignment/matching of semantic artefacts, both at the domain level and at the top level, e.g., by recommending how crosswalks across them should be implemented and enacted
- O1.5: Evolve the descriptions of the technical components for semantic interoperability that were identified in the original EOSC IF
- O1.6: Propose strategies for long-term preservation of semantic artefacts
- O2: Knowledge exchange around Semantic Interoperability
- O3: Recommendations

Enter value on the next line:

Interactions

A list of the actors, semantic artefacts, and concepts that need to interact and are of special relevance to this case study. Brief description of each.

Actors: work roles, systems, etc.

Semantic artefacts: Tools which allow humans and machines to locate, access and understand (meta)data, e.g. vocabularies, metadata standards, ontologies, data dictionaries, etc

Concepts: E.g. metadata catalogue, mapping repository, identifier schemes, and other parts of the conceptual framework for semantic interoperability architecture that was proposed in the [EOSC Interoperability Framework \(pp 37–39\)](#). Could also be concepts that are not part of this framework.

Enter value on the next line:

Semantic Interoperability layer

A *brief* free text description of relevant aspects of semantic interoperability from the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#):

Semantic interoperability can be defined as “the ability of computer systems to transmit

data with unambiguous, shared meaning. Semantic interoperability is a requirement to enable machine computable logic, inferencing, knowledge discovery, and data federation between information systems”

[...]

Besides this machine-based view of semantic interoperability, this layer also requires humans being sufficiently aligned to have satisfactory communication. [...]

Possibly a non-technical + technical description.

Questions:

- What’s the character of the semantic structure(s) -formalised/official semantic structure or locally/informally developed?
- How are the semantic structures applied in practice? As is (strong semantics) or used with local/database specific adaptations and additions
- If access to users: potentials and challenges of increased standardisation?

Enter value on the next line:

Potential use case(s) or user stories

A list of usage scenarios for the semantic artefacts in this case study that could be generalised to other disciplines, systems or regions. Brief descriptions or references. Keeping track of this will support comparisons across case studies.

Comment: Might be useful to allow different levels of granularity, e.g. either of:

- A use case describing the sequence of interactions between actors and semantic artefacts to achieve semantic interoperability.
- A user story describing an action on a semantic artefact and its desired outcome from the perspective of a given user

Enter values on the next line:

Technical Interoperability layer

A *brief* description of relevant aspects of technical interoperability from the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#):

Technical interoperability is commonly defined as the “ability of different information technology systems and software applications to communicate and exchange data”. This definition may be also completed by adding the “ability to accept data from each other and perform a given task in an appropriate and satisfactory manner without the need for extra operator intervention”, that is, with an aspect focused on the complete automation of such data exchange

Possibly a non-technical + technical description.

Enter value on the next line:

Organisational Interoperability layer

A *brief* description of relevant aspects of organisational interoperability from the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#):

[...] organisational interoperability refers to the way in which organisations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals. This type of interoperability is also focused on meeting the requirements of the user community by making services available, easily identifiable, accessible and user-focused.

Possibly a non-technical + technical description.

Enter value on the next line:

Legal Interoperability layer

A *brief* description of relevant aspects of legal interoperability from the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#):

[...] legal interoperability requires [...] that data should be reusable. It concerns the ability to combine datasets from multiple sources without conflicts among restrictions imposed by the license of each dataset

Possibly a non-technical + technical description.

Enter value on the next line:

Sustainability considerations

A list of the most pressing threats to maintaining semantic interoperability in this case study. Brief descriptions of issues related to technical, governance, financial, staffing workforce, etc. Enter value on the next line:

Key take-home points

Successes, barriers, challenges, opportunities, lessons learned, possible areas of future collaborations, etc. Enter value on the next line:

